

FATIGUE MECHANISMS IN HYBRID COMPOSITE
MATERIAL ARALL®-LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Due to its excellent damage tolerance properties the laminated composite ARALL (ARALL will be used in the present paper for ARALL®-LAMINATES, reg. trade-mark of ALCOA, USA) has become an attractive material for future fatigue loaded air space components. In order to take full advantage of the material, the fatigue damage mechanisms have to be thoroughly investigated and suitable fatigue prediction methods have to be developed. In the present paper essential fatigue mechanisms at ARALL are described and a crack propagation prediction method is presented.

INTRODUCTION

The new hybrid composite material ARALL is extremely damage tolerant, and since it had first been presented to the public^{1,2}, and especially after ALCOA, USA, started to prepare the commercial production of the material, the interest of airplane manufacturers has rapidly increased. Weight savings in the order of magnitude of CFRP are expected by the use of this material. Figure 1 shows the build-up of the material. Thin layers of high strength aluminium alloys are bonded together by an aramid fibre reinforced adhesive. Meanwhile different aluminium alloys, different types of fibres and adhesives are also considered to decrease the costs of the material and to increase its efficiency for special applications. From a crack propagation viewpoint the thickness of the individual layers of the material should be low. Presently thicknesses as indicated in Fig. 1 are generally chosen³.

The excellent damage tolerance properties of ARALL are due to the fact that cracks which may initiate in the metallic part of the material are bridged by the aramid fibres which are fatigue resistant and remain unbroken, irrespectively of the fact that the cracks propagate beyond them in the metallic layers. The crack bridging of the aramid fibres reduces the stress intensity of the cracks the longer the cracks grow. Although crack life is prolonged by orders of magnitude due to this mechanism, there are also some beneficial effects in the crack initiation stage.

Further improvement of the crack propagation properties of ARALL can be achieved by the introduction of favourable residual stresses into the material by stretching after the production process.

Fatigue crack propagation in ARALL is controlled by two basic mecha-

nisms which accompany each other, the crack extension in the metallic component of the material and the growth of delamination in the bond between the metal layers and the fibre reinforcement. The analysis of these two mechanisms gives the key to the quantitative prediction of crack propagation. During the past seven years corresponding investigations have been performed at the DFVLR. These led to the development of a crack propagation prediction method^{3,4}.

Fig. 1 Build-up of ARALL.

Fig. 2 Crack initiation behaviour of non-fibre-reinforced materials and of ARALL.

BEHAVIOUR IN THE CRACK INITIATION STAGE

Although the highest benefit of the application of ARALL is reached in the macrocrack stage, there exist also some favourable effects in the crack initiation stage⁵. According to the sequence of the individual stages in fatigue the crack initiation stage is considered first. Figure 2 shows experimental results, where the initiation of cracks at a notch was observed once for ARALL with and without favourable residual stresses and once for a material which consisted of thin aluminium layers only and a non-reinforced bond, and for a material which was purely monolithic. (In the figure the crack extension behaviour at the notch root as well as at the side surface of the specimen is shown.) If the behavior of the notch root is considered first, the crack started in the purely monolithic material in the vicinity of an edge of the specimen. After 13 kcyc the crack became visible at one side surface of the specimen and after 20 kcyc at the other side surface. It is important that the crack expanded undisturbed across the entire notch root.

In case of the specimens made of thin aluminium layers with a non-reinforced bond the crack started in one layer and propagated there for some time until another crack started in the other layer. There existed a clearly visible decoupling effect. A decoupling effect was also observed at ARALL without favourable residual stresses, and the effect became even more pronounced for ARALL with favourable residual stresses. The magnitude of the decoupling effect depended in ARALL to some extent on the stress level which was applied. It was larger at a low stress level. In summary, the decoupling effect was beneficial. Besides that cracks propagate normally slower in thin sheets due to the plane stress condition being present.

MACROCRACK STAGE

In Fig. 3 the fatigue crack propagation behaviour of ARALL with and without residual stresses under TWIST flight by flight loading is shown. Also shown is the behaviour of purely monolithic aluminium specimens and of specimens made of thin aluminium layers with a non-reinforced bond. Although the specimens with thin aluminium layers and the non-reinforced bond showed already some improvements as compared to the purely monolithic aluminium specimens, the macrocrack behaviour at ARALL showed a completely different characteristic and enormous improvements. Artificial favourable residual stresses improved the behaviour further. The figure clearly indicates the advantage of ARALL. ARALL is well suitable for fatigue critical areas of airplanes as lower wing skin, fuselage, Besides that ARALL can be used as crack stopper.

As mentioned before, the crack bridging due to the aramid fibres is the predominant cause for the excellent crack propagation properties. The efficiency of the crack bridging depends on several factors, as the build-up of the laminate, the crack propagation in the metallic layer, the growth of delamination between the metallic layers and the fibre

Fig. 3 Fatigue crack growth of non-fibre-reinforced materials and of ARALL under TWIST loading.

Fig. 4 Delamination growth as function of crack bridging fibre stresses.

reinforcement, the residual stresses being present in the material and the type of fatigue loading (high peak loads, compression loads, etc.). Although the interaction of these individual contributions is highly complex, several important trends could be derived from systematic constant amplitude studies.

1. Crack Propagation Under Constant Amplitude Loading

The investigations at DFVLR showed that the crack extension in the metal component of the material and the shear deformation of the adhesive and the delamination process were the most essential contributions to the crack propagation behaviour at ARALL.

- Crack propagation in the metal component:
Crack propagation in metals and also in the metallic component of ARALL alone can successfully be described on the basis of the cyclic stress intensity factor and an equation of the type $da/dN = C \cdot \Delta K_{eff}^n$. This crack propagation equation is derived from constant amplitude tests on non-reinforced material.
- Shear deformation and delamination growth:
The delamination growth as a consequence of the shear stresses between the metallic layers of ARALL and the fibre reinforcement can be individually studied if a special type of specimens is used, where the metallic layers are completely separated and where the loads, which would have been taken by the metallic layers, are transmitted by shear stresses to the aramid fibres. Constant amplitude loading is applied in these studies. Results are shown in Fig. 4. The results can analytically be described by an equation of the type: $db/dN = C \cdot \Delta G^m$, with b as the delamination size and G as the energy release rate.
- Simultaneous crack and delamination growth:
If a crack propagates in intact ARALL specimens, the crack rate and the delamination growth rate depend on ΔK_{eff} and ΔG , respectively, as indicated before. Important are the instantaneous magnitude of the fatigue stress, the instantaneous crack length, the instantaneous delamination size and the build-up of the material. The procedure for the determination of the effective stress intensity and of the energy release rate is described in refs. 3,4 in detail.

2. Prediction Model for Crack Extension in ARALL

For a quantitative prediction of the crack growth in ARALL the following calculation scheme was developed³:

- The instantaneous cyclic stress intensity factor and the energy release rate are calculated first as mentioned before.
- The cyclic stress intensity factor is then used to calculate a crack growth increment from the basic $da/dN - \Delta K_{eff}$ behaviour for the metallic component of ARALL only.
- The delamination growth per cycle is then calculated using the instantaneous amount of the energy release rate and the basic $db/dN - G$ relationship as shown in Fig. 4.
- The amounts for the increase in the crack length and in the delaminated area for the instantaneous cycle which have been determined as described before form then the basis for the calculation of crack extension during the next cycle. Since the mechanical and geometri-

cal conditions change during crack advance, this has to be accounted for: All crack propagation calculations must be started at the beginning of the fatigue loading.

In Fig. 5 an overview of the described calculation scheme is given. The prediction method has already been applied to various constant ampli-

- Condition before a cycle is applied

- Calculation of crack growth increment

- Calculation of K_{eff}

$$\Delta K_{eff} = f(F, a, b, Lam.)$$

- Calculation of G

$$\Delta G = g(F, a, b, Lam.)$$

- Determination of da/dN from:

- Determination of db/dN from:

Fig. 5 Crack growth prediction method for ARALL - schematic.

Condition after application of the cycle
= starting conditions for the next cycle

tude loading conditions and different types of ARALL specimens. An example of the application of the prediction method is given in Fig. 6.

FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE PREDICTION METHOD

The crack growth prediction method represents a straight forward analysis. Further refinements may be performed. For example, plasticity and viscoelasticity in the bond were not specially considered until now.

Fig. 6 Experimental and predicted fatigue crack growth in ARALL.

Another most essential development would be to extend the method to variable amplitude loading conditions⁶. First results which are already available show that the sequence of loads under variable loading has an effect on the crack propagation in the metal part of ARALL which is different from that on the delamination growth. Further systematic investigations have to be performed.

CONCLUSIONS

- The extremely damage tolerant hybrid composite ARALL[®]-LAMINATES meets rapidly increasing interest as candidate material for fatigue critical parts of future light weight constructions.
- For the design of ARALL components new fatigue prediction methods have to be made available. A prediction method for constant amplitude conditions is described in the present paper, which allows for a wide range of variations of the build-up of ARALL and of the materials which are taken for the individual components of the hybrid composite.
- Future developments of the prediction methods for ARALL should refer to further refinements of the analysis procedure itself and to the consideration of variable amplitude loading conditions.

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